

The Dual Roots of Education: A System that Reflects the Complex Interplay of Community Initiative and State Institutionalization in Southern Vietnam

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Abstract

The development of Vietnamese education has been shaped by numerous factors, including traditional values and national identity the ideological currents of Chinese civilization, the impact of colonialism, and modern globalization trends. Among these, the system's origins profoundly influence the trajectory of Vietnam's educational development. This article analyzes the inception of the traditional educational system in Southern Vietnam. The findings reveal that traditional education in the region had dual origins: community-driven initiatives and state institutionalization. The synergy between grassroots efforts and governmental ideologies laid a solid foundation for the development of an educational system deeply rooted in national traditions - anchored in Confucian learning and geared toward the cultivation of knowledge for the benefit of society and the nation. An analysis of the dual origins of traditional education not only highlights the historical foundation upon which Vietnamese education was built but also offers insight into why colonial efforts to impose a new educational trajectory in this Eastern colony ultimately failed.

Keywords: *educational, examination, Nguyen Dynasty, Southern Vietnam.*

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Introduction

Southern Vietnam is a sacred part of the national territory, holding a strategically important position in the country's economy, politics, culture, and national defense. In recent years, this region has become the subject of study for many scholars and academic institutions both within Vietnam and internationally. Several large-scale research projects have been completed and published as valuable academic works. Prominent among them are the studies conducted under the national-level social sciences program The Southern Region – The Process of Formation and Development, resulting in ten published volumes (Phan Huy Le, chief editor, 2018), and the work The History of the Formation of Southern Vietnam before 1945 (Tran Duc Cuong editor, 2015), among others.

In the body of research on Southern Vietnam, the history of education has been discussed from various perspectives, including its scale, structure, achievements, and impact on the socioeconomic development of each historical period (Multiple Authors, 2021; Ngo Minh Oanh et al., 2019; Hoang Thi Hong Nga, 2015). However, a comprehensive understanding of the educational development in Southern Vietnam remains an underexplored area. A thorough historical study of education in this region is still eagerly awaited by academic and educational institutions, especially by scholars with a deep interest in Southern Vietnam. To contribute to the historical documentation of education in Southern Vietnam, this article compiles and systematizes available materials, and provides an initial evaluation of the formation of traditional education under the Nguyen Lords (1698-1802). This is considered the beginning - the

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foundational stage - of the educational endeavor in a land with a unique historical identity: Southern Vietnam.

Documents and Methodology

This article belongs to the genre of collection and documentary study. The materials used include historical, political, and cultural records of the Nguyen Dynasty, compiled by the *Guó Shǐguǎn* (國史館 – the official historiographical office of the Nguyen court, responsible for researching, preserving historical documents, and compiling official dynastic histories). Key sources utilized in this article include: *Dà Nán Yītǒng Zhì* (大南一統志), *Dà Nán Shí Lù* (大南寔錄), and *Dà Nán Lièzhùàn* (大南列). In addition to the official publications of *Guó Shǐguǎn*, the article also draws upon works by contemporary scholars, such as *Jiāding Chéng Tōng Zhì* (嘉定城通志) and *Fǔ Biān Zá Lù* (撫邊雜錄). It further incorporates findings from recent studies and compilations, including *The Cultural Heritage of Southern Vietnam through the Lens of 18th-19th Century Scholars* (Ca Van Thinh, 2022), *The Southern Region – The Process of Formation and Development* (Phan Huy Le editor, 2018), *Dictionary of Vietnamese Historical Figures* (Nguyen Q. Thang, 2013), *Old Gia Dinh* (Huynh Minh, 2006), *The Nguyen Cochinchina (Southern Vietnam)* (Phan Khoang, 1970), *Vo Truong Toan* (Nam Xuan Tho, 1957), among others.

In terms of methodology, the article employs historical research methods. Historical events are placed within their proper temporal context and interconnected to reconstruct the historical truth of the educational endeavors in Southern Vietnam during the period when the Nguyen Lords served as the ruling authority.

Findings and Discussion

Education Rooted in the People

Historical studies on the Southern Vietnam region have shown that up until the 16th century, this area remained largely undeveloped - dominated by dense forests and sparsely populated by a few indigenous ethnic groups with very small populations (Tran Duc Cuong editor, 2015). However, beginning in the late 16th and early 17th centuries, Vietnamese settlers from the North and Central regions started migrating southward, initiating the process of land reclamation in areas such as Dong Nai and Mo Xoai (present-day Ba Ria), and gradually expanding across the broader Southern territory. In its earliest phase, this southward expansion was entirely spontaneous. Groups of people from North and Central Vietnam, unable to bear the oppression of the ruling powers, left their homelands in search of new lands where they could live in peace. Up until nearly the end of the 17th century, the Vietnamese feudal state had not yet established local governance structures to oversee the population or the expansion effort. Vietnamese history records that it was not until 1698 that the Nguyen Lords officially established a local government in Southern Vietnam. This included the formation of Gia Dinh and Phuoc Long prefectures, Tan Binh district, and the Phien Tran administrative unit. Key administrative positions such as Zhènshǒu (鎮守, Defense Command Governor), Gāibù (該簿, Administration Commissioner), and Jìlù (記錄, Surveillance Commissioner) were appointed to manage local affairs (Tran Duc Cuong editor, 2015).

Although the administrative system was in place, the economic conditions and organizational capacity of the Nguyen Lords' government in The Nguyen Cochinchina (Southern Vietnam) remained limited. The administration primarily focused on safeguarding landownership, suppressing uprisings and looting, organizing land cultivation, and ensuring the people's survival. Education was not yet part of the governance agenda. According to Phan Khoang (1970), the Nguyen Lords in The Nguyen Cochinchina did not establish public schools, district or prefectural academies, but rather allowed private individuals to open schools and teach freely. Le Quy Don (1973) also noted that the Nguyen lords focused solely on maintaining control over a region, only opening provincial examinations and primarily employing their clan members. They did not value intellectuals and thus failed to gather talented and virtuous individuals.

In examinations, the number of students passing the Classical Chinese essay section was five times greater than those in the main category. In important positions, they entrusted the management to their relatives and appointed those who passed the Chinese essay section as assistants. Those who passed the Autumn Exams would begin as district or provincial magistrates, focusing mainly on legal affairs. Record-keepers were mainly in charge of tax matters. Major plans or strategies were not within their reach. As for the common people and young scholars, they were neither nurtured nor guided. Yet, despite all this, the literary tradition in this land remained unbroken - it is truly admirable (Phan Khoang, 1970).

To date, scholars have yet to uncover any documents that detail the scale or organizational structure of education in Southern Vietnam during the period when the Nguyen Lords established their rule. The path to understanding the development of people-led education during this time lies primarily in the lives and work of notable educators who made significant contributions to the region. Their legacies, preserved in historical records, offer important insight - figures such as Vo Truong Toan, Dang Duc Thuat, and other Confucian scholars who greatly contributed to the cultural and social life of Southern Vietnam, including Trinh Hoai Duc, Le Quang Dinh, Ngo Nhon Tinh, Nguyen Dinh Chieu, and Ho Huan Nghiep...

Among these Confucian scholars, Vo Truong Toan stands out as the most prominent contributor to education in Southern Vietnam. He hailed from Hung Hoa village, Binh Duong district, Gia Dinh prefecture, and spent his entire life during the era of the Nguyen Lords (his exact birth year is unknown, but he passed away in 1792). According to *Books Vo Truong Toan* by Nam Xuan Tho (1957), he was a man of profound knowledge and high moral character, uninterested in fame or official position, choosing instead to live in seclusion and devote himself to teaching. His surname was Vo, given name Truong Toan; his birthplace is variously reported as Thanh Ke (Thua Thien) or Binh Duong (Gia Dinh). His teacher is unknown, but his learning had reached a refined and complete level - solid, genuine, with deep expertise and understanding. When the Tay Son upheaval occurred, he went into hiding and opened a school, attracting several hundred students. Among them, Ngo Tung Chau was particularly notable. The most outstanding students included Trinh Hoai Duc, Pham Ngoc Uan, Le Quang Dinh, Le Ba Pham, and Ngo Nhon Tinh. Other respected scholars like Mr. Chieu and Mr. Truc also studied under him, but there are too many to name. These men all came of age during a time of political turmoil and national restoration... and they all accomplished great achievements in life. When Nguyen Anh entered Gia Dinh, he often summoned Vo Truong Toan for discussions. He had heard of his vast knowledge, especially his mastery of the Four Books. Mr. Chieu was a reclusive Confucian who studied under the Teacher, thoroughly grasping the principles of cultivating virtue and nurturing moral energy... The Teacher's learning was truly profound and meticulous - regardless of which classics he read, he grasped their meaning with clarity. The Teacher had no desire for official rank and thus did not leave behind a formal career. From the beginning, he used the study of moral philosophy as a means of education - not only did he train many talented individuals in his time, but he also passed down methods of instruction and scholarship that influenced later generations. Even today, the people of the six southern provinces still uphold values of loyalty and righteousness, willing to sacrifice their lives. While this is due in part to the humane virtue of the monarchs who followed, such widespread moral sentiment would not have been possible without the foundational contributions of the Teacher in nurturing and educating the people in earlier times. (Nam Xuan Tho, 1957).

According to Tran Van Giau (1998), Vo Truong Toan lived in seclusion from the government but not from society. He opened a school and taught hundreds of students, many of whom later passed the imperial examinations and held high-ranking official positions, while others studied simply to live a life grounded in moral principles. Whether they studied to become officials or simply to become better human beings, most of Vo Truong Toan's students embodied the spirited character of the people of Southern Vietnam - righteous and deeply loyal.

In Southern Vietnam, the renowned figures Trinh Hoai Duc, Le Quang Dinh, and Ngo Nhon Tinh were celebrated poets and scholars at the end of the 18th and early 19th centuries. The title *Jiading Sanjia* (嘉定三家, The Three Scholars of Gia Dinh), or *Jiading Sanjia Shi* (嘉定三家詩, The Three Poets of Gia

Dinh), was a name affectionately given by the Southern people to these three men, who were not only key contributors to the development of the southern territories but also made significant contributions to the nation's literature and historiography. The *Jiāding Sānjiā* were admired not only for their talent but also as exemplary figures who dedicated themselves to the advancement of Southern Vietnam (Huynh Minh, 2006).

Besides the *Jiāding Sānjiā*, Vo Truong Toan's students also formed the Hui Shān (會山) (comprising Trinh Hoai Duc, Pham Ngoc Uan, Ngo Nhon Tinh, and Diep Minh Phung) and the Píngyáng Shī Shè (平陽詩社) poetry society (which included Ngo Nhon Tinh, Trinh Hoai Duc, and Le Quang Dinh). Trinh Hoai Duc was regarded as the leader of both the *Jiāding Sānjiā* and the Hui shān, while Ngo Nhon Tinh led the Píngyáng Shī Shè, praised as the most talented calligrapher and painter of his time. Vo Truong Toan's students made no distinction between Vietnamese and Hoa (Minh Huong). All of his disciples were brilliant intellectuals who not only wrote patriotic poems and praised the beauty of Saigon but also devoted their talents to serving the royal court and achieved great accomplishments. Trinh Hoai Duc became Minister of Personnel and concurrently Minister of War, receiving the honorary title Xiézhù Dàxué Shì (協助大學) - a high-ranking official title in the feudal era (originating in the Later Le dynasty and developed further under the Nguyen dynasty), referring to one of the Yuè'nán Sìzhù (越南四柱, Four Pillars of the Court), also serving as a royal advisor and member of the Imperial Council. Ngo Nhon Tinh rose to become Minister of Public Works and concurrently Acting Governor-General of Gia Dinh. Ngo Tung Chau served as a tutor to Crown Prince Canh. Le Quang Dinh was appointed Minister of Finance and director of the Imperial Observatory, while Ngo Nhon Tinh held the title of Minister of Public Works and was also Deputy Governor of Gia Dinh... (Huynh Minh, 2006).

According to Tran Van Giau (1998), Vo Truong Toan's students deeply absorbed an education that was substantive, with profound scholarly expertise and thorough understanding. From those who achieved high academic honors and rose to powerful positions, to figures such as Nguyen Dinh Chieu, Huynh Man Dat, Phan Van Tri (along with Ho Huan Nghiep, Bui Huu Nghia, Truong Dinh, Nguyen Huu Huan, Hoc Lac...), all remained steadfast in their integrity during the time of national invasion -and all were influenced by Vo Truong Toan. When the three eastern provinces of Southern Vietnam fell into French hands, a group of Confucian scholars - including Phan Thanh Gian (also of Minh Huong origin), Nguyen Thong, Pham Huu Chanh, Vo Gia Hoi, and Truong Ngoc Lang - took it upon themselves to erect a tombstone and move Vo Truong Toan's remains from Hoa Hung village (Chi Hoa, Saigon) to Bao Thanh village (in Ben Tre province), the homeland of Phan Thanh Gian. However, while the tombstone was still under construction, the French proceeded to seize the remaining three western provinces of Southern Vietnam. On both the tombstone at Hoa Hung and the one at Bao Thanh, there remains an engraved stone inscription bearing the honorific title conferred posthumously by Lord Nguyen Anh: Vo Truong Toan, the virtuous gentleman of Gia Dinh, revered scholar). This scholar was one of the foremost contributors to cultivating the spirit of Dong Nai - a land known, according to Trinh Hoai Duc (1972), for "its many people of loyalty and heroic spirit, who valued righteousness over wealth - even the women were the same."

Many of Vo Truong Toan's students continued his legacy, advancing education through various paths: teaching, writing poetry and literature, and compiling valuable textbooks and learning materials. Especially in the realm of book writing, many of their works not only reflected deep knowledge and helped readers gain a firm grasp of their subjects, but also nurtured in younger generations a love for the nation and its people, along with a strong spirit of independence and self-reliance. Trinh Hoai Duc authored *Jiāding Chéng Tōng Zhì* (嘉定城通志), an exceptional work on national history and culture that remains valuable today, along with famous poetry collections such as *Gěn Zhāi Shījī* (艮齋詩), *Běi Shǐ Shījī* (北使詩集), and *Dìng Sānjiā Shījī* (定三家詩集) - the latter including poems by Trinh Hoai Duc, Le Quang Dinh, and Ngo Nhon Tinh. Le Quang Dinh wrote *Huáng Yuè Yītǒng Yú Dì Zhì* (皇越一統輿地志) and *Huá Yuán Shīcǎo* (華元詩草); Ngo Nhon Tinh (together with Bui Duong Lich) wrote *Yì Ān Fēngtǔjì Xù* (乂安風土記序), as well as *Shí Yīng Táng Wénjí* (拾英堂文集), *Shí Yīng Táng Shījī*

(拾英堂詩集), and Yītǒng Yú Dì Zhì (一統輿地志). It can be said that Vo Truong Toan's students formed a new class of Confucian scholars imbued with the Dong Nai spirit, dedicated to elevating public knowledge and cultivating talent for the Southern region (Ca Van Thinh, 2022).

Following Vo Truong Toan, another "teacher of masters" in the Southern region during the Nguyen Lords' era must be mentioned: Dang Duc Thuat, whose name is closely associated with the honorary title Dèng Jiā Shǐ Guān (鄧家史觀, Dang family historical school). According to *Dà Nán Lièzhuan*, it is recorded: "Dang Duc Thuat, courtesy name Cuu Tu, his place of origin unknown. In his youth, Duc Thuat was intelligent, widely learned, excelled in poetry, and was especially outstanding in history. Previously, to avoid the Tay Son turmoil, he built a house hidden in the An Phuoc mountains of Binh Thuan and lived in seclusion teaching students. In the ninth year of The To Cao Hoang De (1788, year of Mau Than), after reclaiming Gia Dinh, Duc Thuat came to present himself. Seeing him as a venerable elder and erudite scholar, the king cherished and respected him, appointing him to the Han Lam Institute as a Court Lecturer and Censor. Thuat was upright and outspoken, never hesitating to speak out on matters. Witnessing the severity of flogging punishments, he petitioned for their abolition. When the king refused, Thuat, who stuttered, remarked to others, 'If advice is not heeded, what use is there for a censor?' Thus, he resigned and left office. The king sent the Military Commissioner Tong Phuc Dam to pursue and invite him back. Later, while accompanying a military campaign, he died en route. Previously, when Dang Duc Thuat was residing in Gia Dinh, renowned scholars such as Trinh Hoai Duc, Ngo Nhan Tinh, Le Quang Dinh, and Nguyen Huong, having heard of his poetic fame, came to honor him as their teacher. The flourishing of poetry learning in Gia Dinh began from that point" (Guó Shǐguǎn, 1993). In addition to *Dà Nán Lièzhuan* (Book 1), *Dà Nán Yūtǒng Zhì*, in the section on notable figures of Binh Thuan, also writes about him: Dang Duc Thuat, place of origin unknown, resided in Yen Phuoc district teaching students. In the year of Mau Than, during the early years of the Trung Hung (Restoration) when the great army recaptured Gia Dinh, Thuat, leaning on a staff, came to present himself and was appointed as a Censor. Thuat was forthright and dared to speak on matters, earning the king's favor. Later, he joined the military campaign and died along the way. While Thuat was in Gia Dinh, the likes of Trinh Hoai Duc, Ngo Nhan Tinh, Le Quang Dinh, and Nguyen Huong, upon hearing of his renown in poetry, all revered him as their teacher. The flourishing of poetry learning in Gia Dinh started from then (Guó Shǐguǎn (1959a).

Furthermore, Nguyen Q. Thang (2013) also wrote about this esteemed Confucian scholar: "Dang Duc Thuat, an illustrious official, courtesy name Cuu Tu, was well-versed in historical studies and was honored by contemporary scholars as the founder of the 'Dang gia su phai'. When the Tay Son uprising began, he built a house in Phuoc Son, Binh Thuan province, and lived in seclusion. In the year of Mau Than 1788, he came to Gia Dinh to meet Nguyen Anh and was appointed as a Censor and Court Lecturer at the Han Lam Institute. His character was upright and unyielding; when his counsel was ignored by Lord Nguyen, he said: 'Words that hold no sway, how can one continue in the role of a censor?' Thus, he resigned. Lord Nguyen had to send someone to summon him back before he agreed to return to service. Later, he died in the army and was posthumously honored as Minister and Court Lecturer." When Dang Duc Thuat passed away, Trinh Hoai Duc composed the poem:

*Throughout his days, Tu My oft met fortune's frown.
A soul of rarest gift, yet cast adrift by fate.
Now 'neath the Yellow Springs, where noble spirits crown,
He rises to the throne among the lords of Letters Great.
Soft zithers hum their dirges in the mournful breeze,
While goblets lifted high, spill tears of solemn wine.
His memorials once gave voice to mortal pleas,
His records set the errant chronicles in line.*

*Though he withdrew to the mountain's bush and hidden glen,
The songs of passion lingered, undiminished by the years.
Each night, before his tomb by the lonely shore, again
The angry tides still rise, and the winds still bear our tears.*

The First Marks of State Involvement in Educational Activities in Southern Vietnam

The region of The Nguyen Cochinchina (Southern Vietnam) was established in 1558 with the event of Nguyen Hoang assuming governance over the Thuan Hoa area. Historical records from the Nguyen dynasty state that "When Lord Tien Nguyen Hoang first arrived in Thuan Hoa, he focused on stabilizing security and reclaiming land for settlement, thus there were no educational activities" (Guó Shǐguǎn, 1963). It was not until 1632 that education began to be addressed by the government, with the initiation of examination regulations. Lord Sai decreed that a major examination would be held once every six years, and a minor examination every three years. During the major examinations, organized in the spring, candidates would gather at provincial or district offices for a one-day test. The exam content included composing a poem and writing a chapter from a book. The preliminary round was graded by Zhīfǔ (知府, Prefects) and Zhīxiàn (知縣, District Chiefs), while the final review was conducted by Jìlù (記錄, Surveillance Commissioner). Those who passed were granted a five-year exemption from taxes. Alongside this, there were also Hànzì (漢字) character writing exams (known as Hànyǔ (汉语) examinations). Successful candidates were appointed to positions in governmental offices. Under Lord Nguyen Phuc Lan, examination regulations became stricter. *Dà Nán Shí Lù* (Book 1) records: "Year Bǐngxū (丙戌), 11th year [1646], the examination regulations were established with examinations held every nine years. Students studying for the ching do (main curriculum) and hoa van (Chinese writing) subjects were ordered to present themselves at the provincial offices to sit for the exams" (Guó Shǐguǎn, 1963).

Vietnamese examination history records that in 1646, the Nguyen Lords began organizing examination sessions in The Nguyen Cochinchina. According to *Dà Nán Shí Lù* (Book 1), "Year Dīng hài (丁亥), 12th year [1647], in autumn, month 8, the first examination was opened, with seven candidates passing the ching do exams and twenty-four candidates passing the hoa van exams, all of whom were appointed to official positions." Lord Nguyen Phuc Tan (1648–1687) organized examination sessions in the years Gēng zǐ (庚子, 1660), Dīng wèi (丁未, 1667), Yǐ mǎo (乙卯, 1675), Jǐ wèi (己未, 1679), and Dīng hài (丁亥, 1683). Notably, in the At Mao (1675) examination session, besides the Ching do and Hànyǔ (汉语) subjects, the Tàn kǒuqì (探問口氣, oral examination) examination was introduced, which included questions regarding the state of the military and civilians, as well as the affairs of the Le-Trinh regime. Lord Nguyen Phuc Tran (1687–1691) oversaw the recruitment examination in the year Jǐ sì (己巳, 1689) (Guó Shǐguǎn, 1963). However, these examination sessions were only held in the ancient capital of Phu Xuan (present-day Hue). The Gia Dinh region did not have any examination sessions organized at that time. Candidates from Gia Dinh who wished to participate had to travel on foot to the capital Phu Xuan (Hue, about 700-800 mile).

From the time it was officially established (1698) until nearly 100 years later, the government only began to address education and examinations in Gia Dinh. In 1788, Lord Nguyen Phuc Anh began preparing to organize examinations to select scholars for the purpose of governing the Gia Dinh region. Within that framework, Lord Nguyen Phuc Anh organized several preliminary testing activities for candidates in Gia Dinh. Students were exempted from corvée labor and military service to allow them to focus on their studies.

In 1791, for the first time, the government organized an official examination session in Gia Dinh, resulting in 12 successful candidates. The examination system consisted of two rounds: The first round tested on kinh nghĩa (interpretation of Confucian classics), requiring candidates to write one piece each

based on scriptures and history, and poems based on historical and environmental themes, one for each topic. The second round required the writing of *Zhào shū* (詔書), *Zhì* (製), *Biǎo* (表) (various forms of official documents), using history and environmental themes, with three topics for each category. In this examination, candidates who achieved the top rank were appointed as instructors (*Xùndǎo*, 訓導) or ceremonial students in district offices. Those who ranked lower were titled *Nhieu hoc*. All successful candidates were granted exemption from the personal poll tax, corvée labor, and military service. The examination system in Gia Dinh was modeled closely after that of Phu Xuan (*Guó Shǐguǎn*, 1963).

In 1795, Lord Nguyen instituted reforms to the examination system to "strictly follow the precedents of the former dynasties." The examination process was revised to include three rounds:

First round: interpretation of two passages from the Confucian classics, two historical-themed poems, and two environment-themed poems.

Second round: composition of the *pho* (structured poetry) on historical and environmental themes.

Third round: composing one structured poem and *pho*, one ode on history, and one ode on environmental scenery.

Candidates who passed the first round were eligible to advance to the second round, and those who passed the second round could advance to the third round. Passing any round would result in the candidate's name being recorded and classified into three grades: *giap*, *at*, and *binh*. Depending on which round they passed, candidates were granted different degrees of exemption from labor obligations or appointed to various government positions of higher or lower rank.

After establishing the examination regulations, in 1796, the government organized an examination session in Gia Dinh, resulting in 273 successful candidates, including 205 who passed the first round, 54 who passed the second round, and 14 who passed the third round. Among the 273 successful candidates, Pham Dang Hung stood out prominently. According to the *Dai Nam Liet Truyen*, he was a native of Giong Son Quy, formerly part of Tan Hoa district, Tan An prefecture, Gia Dinh province; later transferred to Go Cong province; and today part of Lang Hoang Gia hamlet, Long Hung ward, Go Cong city, Tien Giang province. He was the son of Pham Dang Long and Phan Thi Tanh. In the year of Binh Thin (1796), at Gia Dinh, he passed the third round of the examination. Pham Dang Hung was renowned for his literary talent and virtuous character and was appointed as a *Le sinh noi phu* (Ceremonial Student in the Inner Court) during the reign of Lord Nguyen Phuc Anh. Later, he was promoted to *Tham luan* (Consultant) at the *Ve Phan Vo* (Phan Vo Guard), where he led troops to fight against the Tay Son army in Phu Yen. In the year of Ky Mui (1799), Pham Dang Hung was appointed *Tham tri bo Lai* (Vice Minister of the Ministry of Personnel), but he often accompanied the army in the capacity of Military Advisor. When Lord Nguyen Phuc Anh ascended the throne, taking the reign title Gia Long (1802), Pham Dang Hung successively held positions such as Vice Minister of the Ministry of Personnel cum *Chuong truong da su* (Chief of Riverworks, 1805), Inspector of the Huong Examination at Kinh Bac (1807), Minister of the Ministry of Rites (1813) concurrently overseeing the *Kham thien giam* (Office of Astronomy, 1815). In 1816, he petitioned the emperor to establish *Xa thuong* (communal rice granaries) to aid the poor during famines, but the proposal was not approved. In 1821, under the reign of Emperor Minh Mang, he was appointed *Pho tong tai* (Deputy Chief) of the *Guó Shǐguǎn*. In the same year, he was demoted two ranks for falsely awarding certificates at the Ministry of Rites. Later, he was reappointed as a Scholar at the *Hàn lín yuàn* (翰林, Imperial Academy), then promoted to Left Vice Minister of the Ministry of Personnel, concurrently managing the Imperial Academy. Not long after, he was reinstated to his previous position at the *Guó Shǐguǎn*, concurrently holding the Seal Custodian of the Ministry of Personnel, and was tasked as Compiler of the Royal Genealogy). In the year of Jiǎ Shēn (甲申, 1824), he was restored to the post of Minister of the Ministry of Rites. In April of the year Yǐyǒu (乙酉, 1825), when the emperor was touring Quang Nam, Pham Dang Hung was appointed as *Chuong quan Kinh thanh Hue* (Chief Administrator of the Imperial Capital Hue). However, on the 14th day of the 6th lunar month of that year (July 29, 1825), he passed away in Hue at the age of 60. In 1849, under the reign of

Emperor Tu Duc (who referred to Pham Dang Hung as his maternal grandfather), he was posthumously granted the titles of Dac tan Vinh loc dai phu, Thai bao, Can chanh dien dai hoc si, and was titled Duc Quoc Cong. He was enshrined in the Trung Hung Cong Than Temple and his name was included in the Hien Luong Temple. His wife was posthumously granted the title Duc Quoc Nhat Pham Phu Nhan, with the posthumous title Doan Tu. At the same time, the emperor ordered the construction of an ancestral hall for the couple at Kim Long (now part of Hue city) and conferred honorary titles on their ancestors (Guó Shǐguǎn, 1993).

In addition to establishing examinations based on traditional education, Lord Nguyen also, for the first time, appointed an educational supervisor (doc hoc) for Gia Dinh. Although nearly one hundred years had passed since the establishment of sovereignty over the region, it was only then that Lord Nguyen appointed the first doc hoc. Nguyen Thai Nguyen - an intellectual among the scholarly Confucian elite - was entrusted with this task. The *Dà Nán Lièzhuan* (Book 2) describes: "Nguyen Thai Nguyen was a native of Huong Tra District, Thua Thien Prefecture; his father's name was Su, a man known for his stubborn righteousness, who served as an official at the Han Lam Institute. Nguyen inherited his father's traits - steadfast, upright, yet gentle and amicable, possessing a similar bearing. In the year Yǐ sì (乙巳, 1785), he followed Nguyen Anh to Vong Cac and was appointed as a royal envoy and advisor. Upon returning to Gia Dinh, he served at the Ministry of Personnel and later transferred to the Ministry of Rites. Even when serving close to the Lord, he always spoke candidly, expressing everything without concealment, which proved truly beneficial. Because he often spoke against the Lord's wishes, he was eventually dismissed. In the winter of the year Yǐ mǎo (乙卯, 1795), Nguyen was reappointed to the Ministry of Rites and concurrently tasked with overseeing education, teaching Crown Prince Canh, and collaborating with Nguyen Bao Tri, Nguyen Tu Chau, and Nguyen Duc Thien to deliberate and formulate examination regulations. In the spring of the year Bǐng chén (丙辰, 1796), an examination was held; Nguyen served as an examiner, selecting successful candidates such as Ngu Khac Minh and Pham Dang Hung, among 14 individuals, all of whom were praised as talents. Nguyen had a fondness for drinking and would sometimes spend entire days drunk. Nevertheless, he was specially granted the honorary title of Minister of Rites, concurrently serving as Dūxué (督學, Provincial Education Commissioner), and was entrusted with approving documents for merchant ships entering and leaving the port. When Gia Long ascended the throne (1802), Nguyen continued to be consulted on important state deliberations. In the third year of Gia Long's reign (1804), Nguyen Thai Nguyen passed away at the age of 74." (Guó Shǐguǎn, 1993).

According to Tran Van Giau (1998), Lord Nguyen had planned to hold another examination in 1799, but it had to be postponed due to ongoing warfare. Therefore, the examination held in 1796 was the last one under Lord Nguyen's rule in Gia Dinh.

Conclusion

Since The Nguyen Cochinchina (Southern Vietnam) was first reclaimed and villages began to emerge, the need for education for future generations had already arisen. However, due to historical circumstances, the state authorities were not yet capable of taking care of the educational cause. For nearly a hundred years, the people themselves took the initiative in managing the education of their children. This was done through various forms - personally teaching their children, hiring private tutors either individually or for a group of relatives; or local scholars opening informal classes in rural villages based on some mutual agreements. Generation after generation, the people of Nam Bo nurtured successors to carry on the legacy of traditional education - teaching moral values, Chinese characters, and Confucian learning. This grassroots, community-driven education system, sometimes quiet and modest, sometimes vibrant and widespread, produced unexpectedly significant results. Many generations of students became learned Confucian scholars, making great contributions to society and firmly establishing a tradition of valuing education among the populace.

Alongside this popular form of learning, the Nguyen Lords in Cochinchina (Southern Vietnam), despite facing countless hardships during the early days of asserting their rule over the newly reclaimed territory,

began to pay attention to education in three key aspects: establishing regulations, organizing examinations, and appointing learned individuals to positions within the administrative system. Though the initial outcomes were modest, their impact was substantial, laying a foundational groundwork for traditional education to take root sincerely in the lives of the people. The attention given by the state combined with the people's aspirations created a crucial premise for the development of traditional education in the new land of Nam Bo.

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